

(Acceptable means of praising the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace) الوسائل المتقبلة في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم

also known as “قصيدة العشرينيات (The poem of the twenties)”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Islamic Jurisprudence, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions

Acceptable means of praising the Prophet may God bless him and grant him peace الوسائل المتقبلة في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم was a poem book composed in honor of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW), dispersed into 28 chapters, one for each letter of the Arabic alphabet that usually appears at the end of every stanza of the poem. The text was earlier composed by Abdurrahman ibn Yakhlaftan at Cordova in 1207-1208, who made every chapter containing twenty stanzas (Ishriniyyat). However, Abubakar ibn al-Muhib added extra stanzas to the poem to complete the total number of five hundred and ninety-five stanzas (595) presented in the historical discussion on the life of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) concerning his moral ethics, physique, and some aspect of the Islamic religious services. The text was adopted widely in most of Africa, where several commentaries were made on it in various languages of Arabic, Hausa, and English to extend its content to the Muslim people. Many people are devoted to chanting the stanzas and memorizing the whole or most of its sections for oral recitation at congregational events or schools to identify significant styles worthy of emulation from the life of the last messenger of Allah (SWT).

Date Range: 1872 CE - 1895 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: أبي بكر ابن المهيب (1988) تخميس الوسائل المتقبلة في مدح النبي المصطفى صلى الله عليه وسلم. مكتبة زكرياء: سلغز كانوا نيجيريا

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ia903002.us.archive.org/14/items/Ishriniyya/Ishriniyya%20%281%29.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: Retrieved from Archives on 1/09/2023 (الديوان وسائل المتقبله في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم (قصيدة الإشرينييات للفازازي

– Source 2 Description: Retrieved from Archives on 1/09/2023 (الديوان وسائل المتقبله في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم (قصيدة الإشرينييات للفازازي

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: . <https://www.noor-book.com/%D9%83%D8%AA%D8%A7%D8%A8-%D8%AF%D9%8A%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%D8%B3%D8%A7%D8%A6%D9%84-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AA%D9%82%D8%A8%D9%84%D9%87-%D9%81%D9%8A-%D9%85%D8%AF%D8%AD-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%86%D8%A8%D9%8A-%D8%B5%D9%84%D9%8A-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%84%D9%87-%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%8A%D9%87-%D9%88%D8%B3%D9%84%D9%85-pdf>

– Source 1 Description: يخلفتن, عبد الرحمن. ديوان الوسائل المتقبلة في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم. كانوا نيجيريا: مكتبة زكريا سلغا, 2017.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: The book was printed on paper.

Number of sheets

– Multiple sheets

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: White paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: Ibn al-Muhib corrected and added stanzas to the original copy of the book.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The text was stored in various locations.

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– Yes

Notes: Many copies of the book are stored in some mosques for the use of the Muslims.

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops
– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– Yes

Notes: Many Muslims kept the book at home for domestic use.

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

Notes: Many handwritten copies were stored in archives and libraries for the benefit of people.

↳ Specify
–Specify: Bookshops

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The book was funded by polity indirectly.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The token incentive is given to the copyist of the book.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The polity established a printing press where the book was published over time.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Some religious duties require an order of the polity.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some political officials assist in the production of the text.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: The political officials and religious officials support each other in some religious duties.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Notes: The text is not scripture, as such laws of the community were not derived from it.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– No

Notes: Religious specialists are in charge of the production of the text.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is not considered religious scripture.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was written in Arabic Language.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 7000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birth rate and death rate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 180000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 80000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 17000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Birth rate and death rate.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text recommended proselytizing to the members of the group.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The reward of proselytizing is reserved in the hereafter.

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no coercion in proselytizing.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is generally done on non-Muslims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The text guided people on proper proselytizing of new members.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text made a vivid statement on proselytizing.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The text is dedicated in praise to the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The front page of the text was accompanied by a frame that surrounded the description of the title, the author, the year of publication, and the publishers.

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: An illustrative frame was made on the front page of the text.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some copies contained commentaries, some were handwritten, some were transliterations to other languages, etc.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: All the multiple versions of the text are considered proper.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Some variations exist in the explanation added to some versions, while some have more pages ahead of others, etc.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions are older than others.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions have explanations and commentaries, while others are plain text.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is made as a single book.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the poems made to praise the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text has religious implications as a guide on some religious services done by the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the literature that describes the behavior of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Other

– Other [specify]: Moral guide

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text contains a guide on some Islamic ritual services.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes some legal codes of Islam reported from the practices of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) in the Islamic State.

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Some institutionalized institutions were attached to the state, as described by the text in many stanzas.

Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Some legal codes dictate the activities of the security forces of the state.

Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Some legal codes dictate the affairs of the judicial institutions of the state.

Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Notes: The text quoted some institutionalized punishments of Islam.

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is meant for those who killed another person unjustly.

↳ Exile?

– Yes

Notes: Exile is designated for those who attacked the authority of the Islamic State.

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment is designed for those who commit fornication and alcohol drinkers.

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

Notes: Ostracism is applied to those who intrude on services not approved by Islam.

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic State is authorized to seize the properties of Zakat (obligatory charity) defaulters.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The text left the reward of services to the administrative body of the state to decide.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar dictates the period of Eid festivals.

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: The Eid festivals are held twice a year.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 1000

Notes: Many people gathered at the Eid ground.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

Notes: Feasting is solely advised to feed the poor.

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: A pilgrimage is required for those who have the strength and finances to attend the event.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: Other reasons are behind the existence of the text.

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

Notes: The pilgrimage is on the directive of the Shari'ah of Islam.

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done at Mecca and its environs.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– No

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done by walking and other means of movement from one place to another.

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: The text did not make a detailed explanation.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The corporal body remains visible, while the soul cannot be seen.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: The material body is subject to perish after death, while the soul remains forever.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Notes: The text did not present much detail on the position of people in the debate.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The space is only known to God.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The religious group of the text affirms the afterlife.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Communicative language in the afterlife is believed to be Arabic.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

– Specify: Majority believed the language to be in Arabic.

Notes: The majority believed the language to be in Arabic.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

– Specify: The minority believed in another language apart from Arabic.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: Human corpses are buried alone.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: Bathing and shrouding of the corps.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The nature of the supreme High God could not be described.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Notes: The relation is only that of the creator and servant.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Supreme High God created everything.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nothing escapes the knowledge of God.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Knowledge of God covers the entire life of humans.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– No

Notes: Emotions of the High God are not visible to humans.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: Omniscient and sovereign.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God communicates to prophet Musa in an awake situation.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God communicates to Prophet Ibrahim in a dream.

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Especially messengers and prophets.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Intuition.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The existence of the human spirit made the life of humans possible in the world.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Humaspirit got to know this world when it was descended to live.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Jinns are present.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are not visible to humans.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - Notes: They do not know what is hidden in the mind.
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels convey God's message to prophets.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Devils whispers to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Emotions of supernatural beings are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: Jinns have a desire for food.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Supernatural beings could move freely from one place to another.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text affirmed the supernatural monitoring of human beings.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: The text affirmed supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence of the humans.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Supernatural monitoring does not require ritual offerings.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not like taboos that go contrary to the directives of the Shari'ah.

↳ Food

– Yes

Notes: Taboo food is declared prohibited.

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about other creatures such as animals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural being prohibits the killing of the coreligionists unjustly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings hate murder of the members of other religions followers unjustly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record it against the person who murdered members of another polity unjustly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: The text described angels not having a desire for sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record lying against who does it.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural monitors record honoring oaths as a rewardable act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate laziness.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate sorcery because of its prohibition by the Shari'ah.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate non-lethal fighting that is not on the Shari'ah directives.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings care about shirking risk for the directives of the Shari'ah to avoid what might hurt human beings.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate disrespecting elders because of the prohibition of Islam on the act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural monitors record it as a sin against the doer.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural monitors record it as a sin against those who practice it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings record rewards on the person who observes them.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: Angels stand by the side of those performing the directed rituals of Islam.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings consider the person an additional member of the development of the religion of Allah.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings considered it recommendable and good.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not like to approach impure person who does not care for their hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record rewards for those maintaining the places of religious services.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings accompany other creatures apart from humans.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings punish infidels on the directives of God.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Contravening to the directives of the Shari'ah leads to supernatural punishment in the hereafter.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: The high god directs the angels to inflict punishment against transgressors.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done by angels in the Hellfire on the directives of the High God.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done in the Hellfire.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done to ensure obedience to the directives of the Shariah.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is reserved for those who refuse adherence to the religion of the High God.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done to enforce moral norms approved by Islam.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done to establish justice in humanity.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: The punishment is severe, only that it does not lead to death.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is even beyond sensory displeasure.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Extreme burning in the Hellfire.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: Some life discomfort could be a consequence of disobedience to the directives of the High God, but the actual punishment is administered in the Hellfire.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Angels file records of good deeds and bad for the High God to award reward or sin.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Imam Mahadi as a savior to believers towards the end of the world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The precise time of coming and whereabouts is not known.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: The savior comes to save believers from the deceptive devil and Dajjal.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

Notes: The sevir restored the Islamic administrative system in the entire world.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: The messiah restored the religious traditions of Islam and its application in the world.

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: The messiah rules out injustice in the world.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Eschaton brings the end of life.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: The actual time is not known.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The actual period could not be identified.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Only God knows the exact time.

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
 - Notes: The end of the world comes at the decree of the High God. Hence, humans could not bring it to an end.

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes

- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
 - Notes: After the eschaton, the world will not be subject to restoration.

- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
 - Notes: Life will continue to exist forever after the eschaton.

- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
 - Notes: Life after the eschaton is only controlled by the High God.

- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
 - Notes: Religion ends at the end of the world.

- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Divine judgment, Hellfire, Paradise, etc.

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No
 - Notes: Only the High God will survive the eschaton.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: The scripture demands celibacy from single, unmarried people.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text demanded that married people engage in light-hearted legal sex.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires obligatory fasting in the month of Ramadan.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends property sacrifice on a charitable basis.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires regular attendance of the congregational services of Islam.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: "Never put yourself in danger," the inscription commands.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommends voluntary meditations and non-obligatory prayers.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 10

Notes: The time depends on the capability of the person.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 1000

Notes: Friday and Eid prayers do not have a limitation of participants but must be above twelve persons.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 168

Notes: Weekly hours of the Friday prayer.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The Friday gathering is scheduled for the afternoon.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are prohibited in Islam.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifice is done at the Eid day and naming ceremony.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned obligatory charity (Zakat).

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: The charity is on the ornaments, money, animals, and farm produce.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Some daily life objects could be given as charity.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Notes: The materials are only given to some identified individuals.

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

Notes: The charitable animals must not have defects.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Charitable donations.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

Notes: Maintenance of the place is done voluntarily.

↳ Other?

– Specify: sweeping.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text emphasized obligatory and voluntary charity as famine relief to the people.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text is set to eradicate poverty through the institutionalized charity of Islam.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated mutual care for the elderly and infirm individuals through the practice of the Prophet (SAW).

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated social welfare through an institutionalized public treasury (Baitul-Mal).

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The group established educational sessions for the members to study the book.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text approved Islamic educational institutions.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended any education that could add value to human life.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The purpose of the text is to educate all followers.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text left education open to all.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is for both male and female sexes.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Education is not restricted to a specific gender.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text did not specify teaching relation to the followers.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text called for respect for the teachers.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The reward of the teachers is in heaven.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated bureaucrats through directives to govern society on the footprint set by the Prophet (SAW).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated bureaucracy permanently by tightening its activities on the administrative style of the Prophet (SAW).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Notes: The text regulated the activities of the bureaucrats permanently.

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed the adherents to ensure mutual obedience to the directive of the bureaucrats as far as did not go against the order of the Shari'ah of Islam.

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated mutual interaction of the people with the members of the other bureaucrats.

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text emphasized the purity of any supporting income before utilization by the state.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Notes: The text established trust in any leasing intersection between the contracting parties.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Notes: The Prophet (SAW)'s leasing habits served as the text's primary means of leasing regulation.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: The text set trust and sincerity to be the foundation of public works.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Notes: The text had not vividly called for a public food storage facility.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: The book adapted the Zakat (obligatory charity) distribution premise from the Qur'anic word regarding food distribution.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated places of civic functions from the adopted practices of the Prophet (SAW).

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated places for the practices of justice through the directives of the prophet (SAW) in any legal adjudication.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for judicious utilization of water for the benefit of humankind.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– Yes

Notes: To govern transportation systems, the text examined the morality of moving from one place to another.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Ethics of speeches.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: The text established a collection of tribute on the non-Muslims under the control of the Islamic state.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: The text required the religious group to charge taxes on unbelievers under the Islamic state's power and to collect tithes on war spoils before it was distributed.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: No institution is allowed to collect taxes on Muslims apart from the Islamic State.

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Notes: The dues collected as tax are used for developmental projects within the state.

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text quoted the warfare of the Prophet (SAW) to defend the Islamic state.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

Notes: Conscript is only applied when an enemy attacks the state unexpectedly.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: The text explained the tactics of the Prophet (SAW) to depend the Islamic state through an institutionalized military corps.

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

Notes: The text stated some strategies for maintaining a standing army to defend the

Islamic State.

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: The text restricted any military campaign to what could lead to the development of the Islamic state.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the charitable donation of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Notes: The food production method of the religious group was not mentioned in the text.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

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